

Erasmus+ Project Redefining nursing skills for ai and robotization in health car

Autonomous Technologies in Nursing Practice (ATNP) scale

Please answer the following questions by determining your ability to interact with autonomous technology on the scale from 1 to 5.

“Autonomous technology” is a class of technology that can interact with the world without human help, such as robots or artificial intelligence.

If you have not dealt with autonomous technology yet, please give answers based on your prediction of how you can interact with it in the future.

How able are you to... 1 = to a very low degree, 2 = to a low degree, 3 = to a moderate degree 4 = to a high degree, 5 = to a very high degree

1	...share ideas related to development of autonomous technologies in nursing practice
2	...consider patients' needs while participating in design of autonomous technologies for nursing practice
3	...consider colleagues' needs while participating in design of autonomous technologies for nursing practice
4	... contribute to formulating ethical requirements for autonomous technologies in nursing practice
5	... recognize own difficulties in dealing with autonomous technologies in nursing practice
6	...recognize colleagues' difficulties in dealing with autonomous technologies in nursing practice
7	...recognize patients' difficulties in accepting autonomous technologies in

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	healthcare
8	...contribute to integrating autonomous technologies in different areas of nursing practice
9	...define risks in relation to an autonomous technology in nursing practice
10	...use autonomous technologies within the nursing process
11	...instruct an autonomous technology in performing tasks related to nursing practice
12	...share tasks with an autonomous technology in nursing practice
13	...monitor the performance of an autonomous technology in nursing practice
14	...intervene in case of an autonomous technology's failure
15	...maintain autonomous technologies in nursing practice
16	...teach colleagues how to use autonomous technologies in nursing practice
17	...teach patients how to use autonomous technologies in healthcare
18	...discuss lessons learned from the use of an autonomous technology with colleagues

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19	... assess usefulness of an autonomous technology in nursing practice
20	...evaluate an autonomous technology in terms of ethical aspects
21	... adapt the evaluation of an autonomous technology in nursing care to different groups of patients
22	... provide informative feedback about an autonomous technology in nursing practice to a responsible person or agency
23	...discuss lessons learned from the use of an autonomous technology with non-nursing specialists (e.g., managers or IT developers)
24	...discuss lessons learned from the use of an autonomous technology with patients
25	... increase your knowledge about autonomous technologies in nursing practice
26	...transfer lessons learned from using an autonomous technology to a different care context